

Detailed description of the **source data file** for the article “Truly pattern: nonlinear integration of motion signals is required to account for the responses of pattern cells in rat visual cortex” by Giulio Matteucci et al.

The “Matteucci_et_al_source_data” compressed folder contains 3 subfolders: **1) “activity”** containing spiking activity data recorded during each extracellular recording session used in the paper **2) “bitcodes”** containing analog and digital data stream produced during each session to temporally align activity with identity and time of stimuli being presented and **3) “stimuli”** containing all frames of all visual stimuli presented to the animals during the recording sessions. The “Matteucci_et_al_source_data” folder also contains a .m file named “sessions_metadata” providing the key metadata for all sessions included in the dataset (e.g., cortical area targeted).

1) “activity” contains two types of files for each recording session: SPIKES and SPIKEMATS .m files.

- SPIKES contains timestamps of every spike detected by the spike sorting algorithm for every manually curated good cluster of each session (expressed in ms) together with the channel on which the cluster was detected. This is the rawest form of data available in these release, raw extracellular traces are too big to be stored in a Zenodo repository (in case of need however they can be requested via email to the corresponding author)

- SPIKEMATS contains the same data already reorganized by using trial timing and identity information contained in the STIM and TIMES files for that same session. For each trial all spikes falling between 200 ms before stimulus onset and 1200 ms after stimulus onset (“SPIKEtimes” variable) or between 800 ms before stimulus onset and 1700 ms after stimulus onset (“SPIKEtimes_bis” variable) were taken. For “SPIKEtimes” variables the first dimension corresponds to stimulus identity, the second to cell identity and the third to trial identity. The variable “SPIKEcounts” contains the count of spike for each stimulus (first dimension), cell (second dimension) and trial (third dimension) identity. “SPIKEmean”, “SPIKEstd” contain the average and std of counts across trials for each unit whereas “basalFR” stores their basal (i.e., average intertrial) firing rate.

In all these variables stimulus identity index corresponds to the integer “bitcode” identifier used during the experiments, ranging in the interval [1,555]. The bitcode-stimulus correspondence is the following:

[1, 40] = spatiotemporally correlated noise movies

[100, 111] = gratings of 0.02 cyc/° and 2 Hz from 0° to 330° of drift direction

[112, 123] = gratings of 0.04 cyc/° and 2 Hz from 0° to 330° of drift direction

[124, 135] = gratings of 0.02 cyc/° and 6 Hz from 0° to 330° of drift direction

[136, 147] = gratings of 0.04 cyc/° and 6 Hz from 0° to 330° of drift direction
[350, 361] = 120° plaids of 0.02 cyc/° and 2 Hz from 0° to 330° of drift direction
[362, 373] = 120° plaids of 0.04 cyc/° and 2 Hz from 0° to 330° of drift direction
[374, 385] = 120° plaids of 0.02 cyc/° and 6 Hz from 0° to 330° of drift direction
[386, 397] = 120° plaids of 0.04 cyc/° and 6 Hz from 0° to 330° of drift direction
[554] = full field flicker (from mid-gray ITI background to black)
[555] = full field flicker (from mid-gray ITI background to white)

2) “bitcodes” contains two types of files for each recording session: ANLG and BCOD STIM and TIMES .m files.

- TIMES contains all detected onset and offset stimulus bitcodes (expressed in s), as used to organize spikes timestamps in the “SPIKEMATS” variables.
 - STIM contains digital bitcode vector data (updated every 66 ms) informing about stimulus identity.
 - BCOD raw single bit encoding of digital bitcode data from which STIM is extracted.
 - ANLG, recording of analog bitcode (recorded at high rate circa 1kHz) for precise information about frame onsets and offsets.
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3) “stimuli” contains folders containing all frames of each stimulus presented to the animals during the extracellular recording experiments. For all grating, plaid and flicker stimuli the frames are stored as single .bmp images in folders named with the bitcode and stimulus properties characteristic of each stimulus. On the other hand, all frames of the noise movies are stored in a .mat file named “0001_to_0040_noise.mat” as an array of size 18x32x1818x40. The first two dimensions of this array correspond to height and width of the image (displayed on screen spline interpolated to full-hd), the third dimension corresponds to frame number within each noise movie and the last dimension corresponds to movie id.